

Decarbonizing primary steel production : Techno-economic assessment of a hydrogen based green steel production plant in Norway

Abhinav Bhaskar*, Rockey Abhishek, Mohsen Assadi, Homam Nikpey Somehesaraei

University of Stavanger, 4036, Norway

Abstract

The use of hydrogen in a direct reduction shaft furnace to reduce iron oxide to metallic iron, and its subsequent conversion to steel in an electric arc furnace has the potential to reduce emissions from the steelmaking process substantially. Approximately 4.26 MWh of electricity is consumed for the production of one ton of liquid steel through the hydrogen based steel making route. Access to cheap electricity could reduce the operational costs, and could lead to the relocation of iron and steel manufacturing units to regions with low electricity prices. Norway has one of the cheapest electricity prices in Europe, and is located in close proximity to major steel demand centers. Techno-economic assessment of a grid connected 1 Mtpa hydrogen based liquid steel production facility, based in Bergen, Norway has been conducted in this work. An optimization framework was developed to evaluate the optimal hydrogen production schedule for five different electrolyzer configurations, to leverage the price arbitrage by using steel tanks for storage of hydrogen. An optimization period of 24 hours was chosen. Historical day-ahead electricity prices from Nordpool were used to develop the optimization model. The levelized cost of steel production varied from \$ 584 to \$989 for the different configurations. Participating in the electricity markets could reduce production costs by 8%, compared to a plant with similar capacity, operating with fixed electricity prices. However, an increase in the electrolyzer capacity resulted in additional capital costs, nullifying the benefits from the reduction in operational costs.

Keywords: Industrial decarbonisation, Hydrogen direct reduction, Water

*Abhinav Bhaskar
Email address: abhinav.bhaskar@uis.no (Abhinav Bhaskar)

1. Introduction

The Inter-governmental panel on climate change(IPCC), has estimated that the total human contribution to global surface temperature increase from 1850–1900 to 2010–2019 is in the range of 0.8°C to 1.3°C, with a best estimate of 1.07°C [1]. The evidence for human-induced climate
5 change affecting the extreme weather events such as heatwaves, heavy precipitation, droughts, and tropical cyclones, and, in particular, their attribution to human influence, has strengthened since the previous reporting period (AR5). High concentration of greenhouse gases such as carbon dioxide, methane, nitrous and nitrogen oxides, halogenated gases and volatile organic compounds in the atmosphere are the main contributors to the increased radiative forcing and consequent rise in global
10 mean surface temperatures. Rapid decarbonisation of all sectors of the economy is imperative to limit the global mean surface temperature increase to 1.5 °C by the end of the century [2].

Approximately 1.86 billion tonnes of steel was produced in 2019 [3]. Primary steel production through the blast furnace basic oxygen furnace route (BF-BOF) contributed to more than 2 GtCO₂ in 2019, which was approximately 6% of the global energy related CO₂ emissions [4]. While material
15 efficiency improvement, product service life extension, increased share of recycling and material substitution are viable measures to reduce steel demand, and hence the associated emissions, steel demand is likely to increase in the short and medium term [5]. Incremental efficiency improvements are likely to contribute to emission reduction but would not be sufficient in meeting the aggressive emission reduction targets required to meet the goals of the Paris climate agreement [6]. Majority
20 of the emissions from primary steel making is from the use of coal, in the ironmaking process. Coke, produced from coal gasification in coke ovens is used to reduce iron oxide and as a high-temperature heat source. Introduction of alternative production technologies with lower or preferably zero carbon-footprint would be essential to decarbonize the iron and steel sector [7]. Hydrogen can replace coke as a reducing agent in a hydrogen direct reduction shaft furnace (H₂-SF) [8]. The resulting direct
25 reduced iron (DRI) can be fed to an electric arc furnace (EAF) for the production of emission free steel. The reduction reaction is endothermic and 99.5 kJ/mol is required for process completion [9]. The reduction steps are presented in the Equations 1, 2 and 3. The conversion of iron ore to

metallic iron occurs at 800-900 °C [10, 11].

There has been a substantial interest in hydrogen based steel production from the research community, policymakers and steel producers. Krüger et. al studied the integration of low and high temperature electrolyzers with the H₂-SF-EAF process, and found that high temperature electrolyzers could lower the specific energy consumption [12]. Vogl et al. conducted a techno-economic assessment of a H₂-SF-EAF system powered by grid electricity, and found that H₂ based steel production could be cost competitive with a BF-BOF based plant at a carbon price of 34–68 EUR per tonne CO₂ and electricity costs of 40 EUR/MWh [10]. The use of existing blast furnaces to integrate higher concentration of H₂ as the reducing agent has been studied by some researchers. Suer et al. analyzed four different scenarios to reduce emissions from existing blast furnaces, based on ISO 14067 framework of cradle to grave analysis. The scenarios included the injection of natural gas or hydrogen into a blast furnace, addition of hot briquetted iron (HBI) into the blast furnace produced from direct reduction of iron ore using natural gas-based and 100% hydrogen [13]. Their analysis revealed that the use of HBI into blast furnaces is a reasonable way to reduce emissions in the short and medium term, and will allow the creation of the hydrogen market till the metallurgical challenges of H₂-SF-EAF based method are completely resolved. To alleviate the problems of storing large quantities of hydrogen, where geological storage sites are harder to find, hydrogen carriers could be used. Andersson et. al evaluated the integration of of four different hydrogen carriers for in the steelmaking process [14]. The four different hydrogen carriers considered were methanol, formic acid, ammonia and perhydro-dibenzyltoluene (H18-DBT) and were compared based on their thermodynamic and economic data to estimate operational and capital costs. Methanol was found to be the most promising alternative.

Approximately 60 kg of H₂ is required for the production of one ton of steel [15]. Hydrogen production through water electrolysis is an energy intensive process and consumes 55-65 KWh/kgH₂.

Availability of low cost electricity is a necessary condition for producing cost competitive H₂-SF-EAF based steel. This creates an opportunity to produce hydrogen at locations with low electricity prices, and high renewable energy potential. Gelen et. al found that the relocation of iron and steel industry
55 to regions with high renewable potential has a significant potential to increase renewable energy deployment while creating more value added through sustainable industrial activities in resource-rich countries [16]. Indirect emissions from H₂-SF-EAF based steel plants depends on the grid emission factor, as depicted in Figure 4.

Norway has one of the lowest wholesale electricity price and energy tax rates in Europe, and has very
60 low grid emission factor, as majority of the electricity is supplied by hydroelectric power plants [17]. Many energy intensive manufacturing industries such as paper and pulp, ferro-alloys and non-ferrous metals (Aluminium) are located in Norway. Almost one-third of Norway's total electricity was used by energy intensive industries in 2019. More than 60% of the industrial electricity demand came from the Aluminium industry [18]. More recently, low-electricity prices, and high-renewable energy
65 potential of Norway is being leveraged by the ammonia producers to reduce emissions from the ammonia value chain. A collaborative project between Yara, Aker Clean Hydrogen and Statkraft called HEGRA has been announced recently [19]. Hydrogen will be produced from water electrolysis, and will decarbonise Yara's ammonia factory on Herøya in Porsgrunn. Apart from the benefits of cheaper electricity and emission free electricity, Norway has an additional advantage of having access
70 to a highly skilled work force from the metallurgical industry. It's proximity to the steel demand centers in the EU could result in lower transportation costs for finished steel. Interestingly, import of iron and steel, cement, ammonia, aluminium and electricity are included in Eu's carbon-border adjustment mechanism [20]. Low emission steel produced in Norway could become cost competitive with other exporters such as Russia, China, India etc. which are still reliant on emission-intensive
75 manufacturing processes.

Apart from abundant hydropower resources, Norway has very good wind potential (both onshore and offshore). The theoretical potential of Norway's offshore is close to 12000 TWh/year, although most of it is located in deep waters and hence costlier to exploit [21]. The recent 4.5 GW tenders for fixed bottom plants in Sørilige Nordsjø II, and floating bottom offshore wind projects in Utsira
80 Nord are an example of the new developments in the Norwegian offshore wind industry. New areas will be opened for auctions in the future, creating a business case for the development of Power-to-X

projects. In order to assess these opportunities better, we have developed a the techno-economic assessment mode of a grid connected H₂-SF-EAF plant in Norway, which procures electricity from the day ahead markets. To the best of the knowledge of the authors, techno-economic feasibility of hydrogen based iron and steel production in Norway has not been analyzed before. Rest of the paper is structured as follows. We present the research framework and methodology in Section 2. Results of the analysis are presented in Section 3, followed by a discussion on the monthly and seasonal variation of electricity prices in Section 4. Conclusions of this study are presented in Section 5.

2. Methodology

A techno-economic assessment (TEA) of the H₂-SF-EAF production system in Bergen, Norway was conducted, based on the TEA framework for green chemical production technologies at low technology readiness level developed by Thomassen et al [22]. First, market assessment of green steel was conducted, based on the commitments made by the automotive and renewable energy generator developers, as well as in light of the recent Fit for 55 regulations and policies announced by the EU. A conceptual process model of a grid connected H₂-SF-EAF was developed to calculate the material and energy balance across different components and for preliminary sizing of the components. The model was used to calculate the annual energy consumption, emissions and material requirement for a steel plant with an output capacity 1 Mtpa of liquid steel. Most energy-intensive industries sign long-term corporate power purchase agreements with power distribution companies to meet their electricity demand. However, the flexibility to produce and store hydrogen at times of low-demand, and low electricity prices could reduce the operational costs of the plant. In this analysis, we have assumed that electricity is procured from the day-ahead market. Historical day-ahead prices for Bergen were retrieved from the NordPool dataset [23]. Electricity prices are available at an hourly resolution different bidding zones in the Nordic electricity markets, including Oslo, Kristiansand, Bergen, Molde, Trondheim, and Tromsø. Bergen was chosen for the present analysis as it has the largest maritime port in Norway, handling more than 36% of the total cargo. As most of the iron ore will be imported, and the finished products would be shipped to EU countries, access to shipping routes could play a pivotal role in site selection. Historical day-ahead electricity prices were used to develop an optimal production schedule for the electrolyzers. Storage sizes were calculated based on the electrolyzer operation profile. Five different electrolyzer configurations were evaluated in this work. In the base case, the output of the electrolyzer system was considered to be equal to

the hydrogen demand from the steel plant. The hydrogen output capacity was increased to five times the hourly hydrogen demand in the highest configuration to evaluate the impact of increasing the electrolyzer size on the financial feasibility of the plant. Based on the preliminary sizing of the components derived from the process model, electrolyzer configurations, hydrogen storage size, and the production profile of electrolyzers, the CAPEX and OPEX for the plant were calculated. Discounted cash flow analysis was conducted to calculate the levelized cost of production (LCOP) of steel. Open-source scientific computation software such as Pandas, Numpy and Matplotlib were used in this work [24, 25, 26]. The Ipython notebook environment was used to write the python scripts [27]. The optimization model was written in Python, using PYOMO, which is an open-source optimization framework [28]. The python scripts and data used for the analysis are made available on the Zenodo repository [29].

2.1. Market Assessment

More than 150 MT of steel used in the EU in 2019 [30]. Approximately one-third of it was used in the construction sector. The automobile and machinery sector are the two other major demand segments. In the construction sector, the focus has shifted towards embodied emissions, which includes structural steel. A global coalition of public and private organizations, called the Industrial deep decarbonisation initiative (IDDI) was set up recently to stimulate demand for low carbon industrial materials [31]. The objectives of IDDI include encouraging governments, and the private sector to buy low carbon steel and cement, and to share data and resources to set common standards and targets across member states. The recent announcements to lower the cap in the EU emission trading system, carbon border adjustment taxes, and emphasis on the use of climate-neutral industrial products could result in an increased demand for green steel in the future [20, 32]. Leading automobile manufacturers are moving towards green steel. Volvo, which is a leading automobile manufacturer, and steel producer SSAB have signed a collaboration agreement on research, development, serial production and commercialization of the world's first vehicles to be made of hydrogen reduction based steel. Volvo plans to start the production of concept vehicles and components from hydrogen based green steel by 2021 [33]. Similar, plans have been announced by the Mercedes group, which has invested in an upcoming 5 Mty⁻¹ steel production facility in Sweden [34]. Ørsted, a leading wind energy developer has recently joined the SteelZero global initiative to drive market demand for net-zero emission steel [35]. The energy transition commission has

published a detailed report on policy measures, which could further stimulate the demand for green steel across the value chain [36].

2.2. Conceptual process modelling

145 Hydrogen based steel production can be divided into three distinct sub-processes i.e. production and storage of reducing agent (hydrogen), direct iron production in the shaft furnace, and conversion of iron to steel in the EAF. Material and energy flows through the different components were calculated for the production of one ton liquid steel. The specific heat and enthalpy of the different species were calculated using the Shomate equation, as described in Equation 4 and 5. The coefficients of
 150 the Shomate equations were taken from NIST webBook [37]. A conceptual model of the system is presented in Figure 1.

$$C_p^\circ = A + B * t + D * t^2 + D * t^3 + E/t^2 \quad (4)$$

$$H^\circ - H^\circ_{298.15} = A * t + B * t^2/2 + D * t^3/3 + D * t^4/4 - E/t + F - H \quad (5)$$

For hydrogen production, an alkaline electrolyzer based hydrogen production system has been considered. Although there has been increasing interest in the polymer electrolyte membrane electrolyzers, alkaline electrolyzers are currently 40% cheaper, and are ready for industrial scale
 155 deployment. Alkaline electrolyzers are being used to produce hydrogen for the demonstration plant commissioned in Sweden in August, 2020 [38]. The main characteristics and costs of the three main types of electrolyzers available in the market i.e. Alkaline, Proton electron membrane (PEM), and Solid oxide electrolyzers (SOEC) is presented in Table 1. The electrolyzer system costs comprise of electrolyzer stack costs, balance of plant equipment like the hydrogen separators, compressors,
 160 electricity conversion devices (transformers and rectifiers), hydrogen purification system, water supply and purification, cooling equipment and the commissioning costs. The costs of shipping the equipment, civil works and site preparations are additional to these costs. With the combined effects of technology learning, standardization of manufacturing components, automation of production processes, and improvements in performance parameters (lifetime, efficiency and durability), the
 165 capital costs of the electrolyzer systems could reduce by 80% in the next three decades [39, 12].

Standardization and technology learning from the chlor-alkali industry could be directly applicable to the water-electrolyzer industry. Nel hydrogen, which is one of the leading electrolyzer manufacturers, has set target of producing hydrogen at \$ 1.5/kg by 2025, which would require significant reduction in electrolyzer costs [40].

Figure 1: Schematic of a grid connected H_2 -SF-EAF based steel production system

170 Hydrogen produced from the electrolyzer can be directly fed to the DRI shaft reactor or stored for
later use. Hydrogen can be stored on-ground in steel tanks or in underground geological storage
sites like salt and rock caverns, aquifers, or depleted oil and gas wells. Salt caverns are most suited
for hydrogen storage and have been used previously in Texas (USA) since 1983 and in Teesside (UK)
since 1972 [41]. Dilara et al. studied the technical potential of hydrogen storage in salt caverns in
175 Europe [42]. They estimated the total onshore and offshore H_2 storage potential to be 84.8 PWh_{H_2} .
Equinor ASA and SSE thermal are building a salt cavern based hydrogen storage facility With
an initial expected capacity of at least 320 GWh at Aldbrough. The storage plant is likely to be
commissioned by 2028 and will comprise of nine salt caverns [43]. Under the HYBRIT project in
Sweden, a lined rock cavern is being developed for hydrogen storage [38]. Since the storage capacity
180 required for the operation of the plants was not very high, surface storage tanks made of seamless

steel or aluminium have been considered in this analysis. A capital cost of 1500 USD/kgH₂ has been considered for the system comprising of the compressors and storage tank [44].

The hydrogen stream, exiting the electrolyzer or storage tank is pre-heated to the reactor temperature of 900°C. Part of the thermal energy can be supplied by exchanging heat with the DRI exhaust, which is primarily composed of steam at a temperature of 350 °C. A high metallization rate of 94% is achieved inside the DRI reactor. The reduced iron can be fed directly to the electric arc furnace for conversion to steel through the HOTLINK[®] or HYTEMP[®] process developed by MIDREX and ENERGIRON technologies respectively [45, 46]. Carbon, from biogenic sources is added in the EAF to meet the metallurgical requirements and for generation of carbon monoxide (CO), which plays an important role in slag formation and removal of impurities [47]. It is also used for the reduction of FeO to metallic Fe. The molten steel stream exits the EAF at a temperature of 1650 °C. Detailed description of the conceptual process model and the material and energy flows through the different components were presented in our previous research article [48].

Table 1: electrolyzer characteristics

Characteristics	Current			2050		
	Alkaline	PEM	SOEC	Alkaline	PEM	SOEC
Outlet pressure (bar)	30	30-50	10	>70	>70	>20
Temperature(°C)	60-90	50-80	700-1000	60-90	50-200	700-1000
Lifetime(thousand hours)	60	50-80	<20	100	100-120	>80
Efficiency (KWh/kgH ₂)	50-78	50-83	45-55	<45	<45	<40
Capital cost (electrolyzer system) (\$/KWe)	500-1000	700-1400	>2000	<200	<300	<200

2.3. Optimization framework

The operation scheduling of the electrolyzers has been formulated as a linear optimization problem, shown in Equation 6.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Minimize} && c_1x_1 + \dots + c_nx_n \\
& \text{subject to} && a_{11}x_1 + \dots + a_{1n}x_n \geq b_1 \\
& && \vdots \\
& && a_{m1}x_1 + \dots + a_{mn}x_n \geq b_m
\end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

The objective of the optimization framework is to minimize the operating cost by utilizing the fluctuations in electricity prices. In our analysis the electricity price is the cost vector c_i , which varies each hour, based on the historical day ahead prices. At each hour, a decision has to be made regarding the amount of hydrogen to be produced, which is represented by the decision variable x_i . The optimization is done for every twenty four hours, since day-ahead prices are available for the next 24 hours. In order to get the annual hydrogen generation profile, the slice of the cost vector is passed to the optimization function, which generates an instance of the optimization problem for every 24 hours. To calculate the annual operational cost the code is run 365 times, as the optimization interval is fixed at 24 hours. The analysis was conducted for all five electrolyzer configurations. The quantity of hydrogen produced per hour is constrained by the installed electrolyzer capacity, defined in Equation 7.

$$0 \leq x_i \leq \text{electrolyzer capacity} \tag{7}$$

The second constraint pertains to the meeting the demand of hydrogen. At each hour, the demand for hydrogen, represented by b_i has to be met. Hydrogen could be supplied by the electrolyzer or through the hydrogen storage unit. Considering the fixed demand of hydrogen for steel making to be d tons/hour, the demand vector is presented in Equation 8:

$$b_j = \sum_{n=1}^{24} d * n; \text{ where } j \text{ varies from } 1 \text{ to } 24 \tag{8}$$

The generation profile is used to evaluate the storage status by transferring all excess hydrogen generated to the storage unit. The costs associated with the compression and transport of hydrogen from the electrolyzer have not been considered in this model. The storage status at each instance can be calculated using Equation 9

$$s_k = \sum_{n=1}^k x_n - d_k; \tag{9}$$

Where $s = 0, t = 0, k$ is the hour, which varies from 1 to 8760.

2.4. Economic evaluation

The capital costs for the main plant components (electrolyzer, storage tanks, DRI reactor, EAF) were calculated for a 1 Mtpa steel production plant. Equipment costs were converted to total capital costs using the Lang factors approach described by Sinnott et. al [49]. A lang factor of two was considered for the entire system. For the electrolyzer system, 35% additional costs were considered for balance of plant costs. A plant life of 20 years was considered for the calculations. The operational costs are comprised of the cost of iron ore, electricity, emission costs, and shaft furnace and EAF operational costs. The electricity costs were determined using the optimization framework described in section 2.3. Only the direct emissions from the plants were used to evaluate the annual emissions cost. The annual maintenance cost was considered to be 1.5 % of the capital cost, and a labour cost of 20\$/tls was considered in the model [49]. The levelized cost of production (LCOP) was calculated using Equation 10 and 11. The economic assumptions are presented in Table 2.

$$LCOP = \frac{C_{capex} * ACC + C_{opex} + C_{maint} + C_{labour} + C_{emission}}{Annual\ steel\ production} \quad (10)$$

$$ACC = \frac{r * (1 + r)^n}{(1 + r)^n - 1} \quad (11)$$

Table 2: Assumptions used in the techno-economic assessment model

Capital cost assumptions			
Equipment	Cost(\$)	Lifetime	Reference/remark
electrolyzer (\$/kW)	700	90000 hours	[50]
Hydrogen storage tank (\$kg/h ₂)	1500	20 years	[51]
Stack replacement cost (\$/kW H ₂)	350	NA	[50]
Shaft furnace (\$t/DRI/year)	240	20 years	[12]
Electric arc furnace (\$t/steel/year)	140	20 years	[10]
Operational cost assumptions			
Item	Cost	Unit	Reference/remark
Iron ore	110	\$/t	[52]
DRI OPEX	12	\$/tls	[53]
EAF OPEX	33	\$/tls	[53]
CO ₂ emission	70	\$/tCO ₂	[54]

3. Results

3.1. Hydrogen production and storage status

The H₂-SF-EAF plant has an hourly hydrogen demand of approximately 7 tons/hr. The plant is constrained to meet the hourly demand, either through generation or from storage tanks. As
215 additional operational costs associated with the storage of hydrogen (compression and transport) have not been considered, the optimization algorithm chooses to produce excess hydrogen, whenever the electricity prices are low. In Figure 2, distribution of generation and storage status for different configurations is presented. It can be observed that, as the electrolyzer capacity increases, the frequency of hours with zero H₂ generation increase. By increasing the capacity from 7 t/hr to 14
220 t/hr, electricity demand is shifted for more than 43% of the time. However, if electrolyzer capacity is increased to 35 t/hr, the electrolyzers remain idle for 74% of the time and are operate at full capacity for 16% of the total hours. The shifting of industrial electricity demand, often referred to as demand response, has the potential to increase the flexibility of the grid and allow integration of integration of intermittent renewable electricity generators [55, 56]. Hydrogen storage tanks remain
225 empty for shorter duration, only 16% of the time for the 35 t/hr electrolyzer configuration. While

they remain empty for 34% of the time for the 14 t/hr configuration. The storage capacity required for the 35 t/hr configuration was 133 t/hr, corresponding to 19 hours of hydrogen demand.

Figure 2: Distribution of hydrogen production and storage for different electrolyzer configurations.

3.2. Energy consumption

In the base case, the H₂-SF-EAF system has a specific energy consumption (SEC) of 4.26 MWh/tls, at an electrolyzer efficiency of 55 KWh/kg H₂. In the literature, the SEC value of comparable systems vary from 3.48 MWh/tls [10, 38] to 3.95 MWh/tls [12]. The difference in the SEC's originate from the use of different values of electrolyzer efficiency (depends on the projected installation year of the plant), use of scrap in the EAF, thermal energy requirements of the shaft-furnace, purge-gas requirements etc. Water electrolysis consumes 76.9% of the total energy. The EAF consumes 0.550 MWh/tls. The DRI shaft furnace consumes approximately 0.780 MWh/tls for heating the hydrogen stream from electrolyzer to the SF reaction temperature. Heat is recovered from the DRI exhaust to heat the incoming hydrogen stream. Variation of the SEC with the electrolyzer efficiency is depicted in figure 3.

Figure 3: Variation in the SEC of the system with variation in the electrolyzer efficiency.

3.3. Emissions

The total emissions from the system could be divided into direct and indirect emissions. Direct emissions from the pellet making process, emissions from the EAF(lime production and use of graphite electrodes) account for 186 kgCO₂/tls. Indirect emissions from electricity consumption

are almost negligible as the grid emission factor of Norway is very low. A comparison of the total emissions from the H₂-SF-EAF operation in different countries is shown in figure 4. It is evident that in countries with low grid emission-factors, the total emissions from H₂-SF-EAF, both direct and indirect, are lower than the emissions from the baseline technologies (BF-BOF and natural gas powered DRI-EAF process).

Figure 4: Emissions from the proposed HDRI-EAF system in different countries. The electrolyzer efficiency is fixed at 55 kWh/kg H₂. The grid emission factors were taken from Moro et. al [17].

3.4. Levelized cost of steel production

The LCOP varies from \$584 to \$989 for the different configurations, shown in Figure 5. The cost of a comparable system using a fixed price of electricity (\$ 60/MWh) has a LCOP of \$636. Almost 73% of the LCOP is comprised of the operational cost, which is primarily composed of the electricity costs. While, the operational costs have the maximum contribution to the production costs at lower hydrogen output capacities, the contributions from capex become more prominent for the

configurations with higher electrolyzer capacities. The maintenance costs increase with higher capacities, while the labour and emission costs remain constant for all configurations at \$20 million and \$10.64 million respectively. The emission costs are calculated only for the direct emissions from the H₂-SF-EAF system.

Figure 5: Levelized cost of variation for different configurations.

The contribution of capex to the LCOP varies from \$ 154 to \$ 505. The main contribution to the capex of H₂-SF-EAF system is from the electrolyzer system. Approximately 388 MW of electrolyzer capacity is required in the base case. The installed electrolyzer capacity scales up linearly with the hydrogen output. The total capital cost for the different configurations, including the installation costs, vary from \$ 367 million to \$ 1.83 billion, for the lowest and highest hydrogen output configurations respectively. Major improvements are expected in the cost and performance of the electrolyzer systems, which could result in lower capital costs in the future [57]. At an electrolyzer cost of \$ 200/kW, and efficiency of 75%(45 KWh/kgH₂), the electrolyzer system costs could decline by more than 75% for the same hydrogen output. 40% of the electrolyzer system capex is incurred for stack replacement after the first ten years. The SF and EAF cost \$ 240 million and \$140 million respectively. The hydrogen storage costs vary from zero in the base case to \$ 199.5 million for the configuration with the 35 t/hr hydrogen output capacity.

270 Electricity costs are the main contributor to the opex of the plant, along with the cost of raw iron
 ore. Hydrogen production is the most energy intensive process. The difference in operational costs
 for the different configurations becomes evident, when the electricity prices are aggregated over a
 month for different configurations, as shown in Figure 6. The annual electricity costs associated
 with hydrogen production vary from \$156 million to \$144 million for the lowest (7 t/hr) and highest
 275 (35 t/hr) electrolyzer capacities, as shown in Figure 7. The difference in electricity costs become
 less pronounced, as the production capacities are increased. If the optimization period is increased
 from 24 hours to 720 hours, the annual electricity costs decrease to \$136 million. Apart from the
 variation in costs for different configurations, there are significant monthly variation in costs. A
 detailed analysis of the electricity price fluctuations and strategies to leverage the temporal price
 280 arbitrage is presented in Section 4. Additional electricity consumption by the SF and EAF remain
 same for all configurations, as they are continuous processes and cannot be shifted in time. The
 operation and maintenance of the SF and EAF cost \$13 and \$32 million annually.

Figure 6: Monthly electricity costs incurred for the generation of hydrogen from different electrolyzer configurations.

Figure 7: Annual electricity costs for different plant configurations.

A global sensitivity analysis was conducted to evaluate the contribution of uncertainty propagation in LCOP values by variation in the discount rate, iron ore price, capex of electrolyzer system, and H₂ storage systems and the electrolyzer efficiency. Electrolyzer configuration with the minimum and maximum capacity are depicted here. The results of the global sensitivity analysis in the form of first order Sobol indices, and total order Sobol indices are presented in Table 3 . The values of the second order Sobol indices were found to be insignificant, indicating weak interaction between the input variables. Iron ore price and electrolyzer system costs have the maximum contribution to the variance in the LCOP. Storage cost does not have a huge impact owing to their relatively smaller size. For configurations with lower electrolyzer capacity, iron ore prices have a higher contribution to the total uncertainty.

Table 3: First order and total order Sobol indices calculated to quantify the uncertainty propagation in LCOP values

Parameters	Lower bound	Upper bound	Unit	Electrolyzer capacity(t/hr)	First sobol indice	Total sobol indice
Discount rate	0.05	0.08	%	Lowest	0.01	0.01
Iron ore cost	70	200	\$/t	Lowest	0.89	0.89
Storage cost	1000	1500	\$/kg\ce{H2}	Lowest	0.00	0.00
Electrolyzer cost	100	700	\$/kW	Lowest	0.08	0.09
electrolyzer efficiency	0.6	0.8	%	Lowest	0.00	0.00
Discount rate	0.05	0.08	%	Highest	0.03	0.03
Iron ore cost	70	200	\$/t	Highest	0.28	0.28
Storage cost	1000	1500	\$/kg\ce{H2}	Highest	0.00	0.00
Electrolyzer cost	100	700	\$/kW	Highest	0.66	0.66
electrolyzer efficiency	0.6	0.8	%	Highest	0.02	0.03

4. Electricity price data characteristics

The current work focuses on developing an optimization model, based on linear optimization techniques for operational scheduling based on day ahead electricity prices. Further insights can be derived by understanding the seasonal variation in electricity prices which can aid in developing an optimal strategy for plant / storage sizing as well. The combination of high degree of variability in electricity demand and supply creates a regional price environment that may have daily, weekly, seasonal or yearly characteristics. This section provides a brief of the price characteristics in Bergen region of Norway for the year 2019 which has been used for the optimization performed in this study.

Figure 8: Seasonal variation of electricity prices in Bergen (2019) and the regime changes based on the Corrected Arc Crossings (CAC).

The electricity prices for the Bergen region in the year 2019 is shown in figure 8. Analysing a time series like the electricity prices shown in figure 8 involves data mining to extract knowledge from the data. One of the methods to gain a deeper understanding of the data and extract patterns and anomalies embedded in the dataset, is Time Series subsequences All-Pairs-Similarity-Search (TSAPSS). Matrix profile is a innovative and fast technique for performing TSAPSS proposed by
 305 researchers at University of California, Riverside and University of New Mexico [58] in 2016. Briefly, the Matrix profile of a time series of length n is itself a time series that contains the the z-normalised

Euclidean distance normalised distance of a subsequence of length m to its nearest neighbor in the original time series [59]. Annotating the original time series with the matrix profile can help locate
310 the motifs (closely repeated patterns) and discords (anomalies). Further, the matrix profile allows us to perform semantic segmentation and identify the existence of regimes in a time series based on the calculation of a Corrected Arc Crossing (CAC) for every data point in the series [60].

The matrix profile for the time series in this study was computed with a subsequence length of 1 week ($m = 24 * 7 = 168$). Based on the matrix profile, the CAC and the locations of the regime
315 change has been plotted in the lower half of figure 8. Figure 8 shows that the major seasons (summer and winter) form a distinct price regime, while the shoulder seasons are split roughly in the middle indicating a transition period. A future work could investigate leveraging the existence of these seasonal regimes for calculating optimum storage sizing and exploring the possibility of incorporating large scale subsurface storage. Large scale storage systems like salt caverns which are
320 cycled seasonally enable continuous production of Hydrogen for extended periods. Additionally, this can be an effective strategy for de-risking against price fluctuations in the electricity market.

Figure 9: Expanded view of the patterns found through motifs(a-c) and the anomaly located through discord(d).

The motif and discords extracted from the price data are shown in figure 9. From the pattern matches obtained in figure 9a and 9b we can see that these weekly periods represent periods with very low daily fluctuation on prices with bi-modal peaks. The twice daily peaks can be attributed to morning and evening peak load periods, however, it is interesting to note that the dips between these periods remains relatively low. The third motif (figure 9c) has similar characteristics however, the peaks during the first two days are much higher. The black anomaly shown in figure 9d is interesting since there is no clear daily pattern in this period and very high variability. A

future work could also explore the utilization of motifs (repeated patterns) and discords (anomalies) in the price data. The current analysis has been done for patterns of sub-sequence length: 1 week. Performing the analysis at varying sub-sequence lengths relevant to the operation of the plant could lead to significant insights. For instance identifying the nature of anomalous periods and linking them to prevailing regional and environmental conditions can help us predict these periods. As mentioned previously, over one-third of electricity generation in Norway is used for energy intensive industrial applications. Performing a similar analysis with electricity price data overlaid with wind/solar energy generation potential on a regional basis can further aid the case for greater investments in renewable energy production to facilitate the development of decarbonized heavy industries in Norway.

5. Conclusion

In this work, we conducted techno-economic assessment of a grid connected H₂-SF-EAF plant in Bergen, Norway with a production capacity of 1 Mtpa for five different electrolyzer configurations. To reduce operational costs, it was assumed that electricity is procured from day-ahead electricity markets. A linear optimization framework was developed to calculate the optimal production schedule for the different electrolyzer configurations to minimize the electricity procurement costs. Levelized cost of steel production was calculated based for the different configurations. Following inferences can be drawn from the analysis:

- The levelized cost of steel production varied from \$ 584 to \$989 for the different configurations. It was found that participating in the electricity markets could reduce production costs by 8% compared to a plant with similar capacity, operating with fixed electricity prices.
- Increasing the electrolyzer capacity reduced the operational costs. However, the fluctuation in electricity prices were not large enough to justify additional electrolyzer and hydrogen storage capacity. The capital cost of electrolyzers and storage remain high.
- Increasing the electrolyzer capacity led to a decrease in operational costs by 3.5% between the highest and lowest configuration. However, it led to an increase in the total plant capex by a factor of 2.32.
- Access to underground geological storage such as salt cavern, rock cavern or depleted oil wells

could make it economically feasible to store large quantities of hydrogen at cheaper costs and allow the plant to leverage the seasonal fluctuation in electricity costs. It would also open opportunity for the steel plant to participate in the electricity capacity markets and generate additional revenue.

360

6. Data availability

Python codes used for modelling the H₂-SF-EAF system and calculating the optimal electrolyzer production schedule are available at Zenodo repository [29].

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